

Data-driven analysis of factors affecting headline secondary school performance measures in England

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Abstract

Secondary school performance measures (SPMs) were introduced in England 32 years ago and have become fundamental metrics affecting schools' policy, funding, and choice. SPMs are at the heart of the school accountability system, described as having three main elements: (i) identifying school underperformance and shaping subsequent interventions, (ii) contributing to the school inspection system and (iii) informing parental choice. While they are well established as a central component of the English education system, SPMs have been, and continue to be, subject to numerous critiques and criticisms. In this analysis we use empirical data and a range of digital quantitative analysis approaches to explore the nature, extent and breadth of the concept of 'performance' as represented by SPMs. We empirically identify limitations in the range of latent variables captured by SPMs and the influence of factors not directly related to 'performance' upon school performance metrics. This study suggests potential in the use digital analysis approaches, including cluster analysis, to better understand the complex interactions of a range of factors which underpin SPMs. In doing so we contribute to discourse around the design and operationalisation of SPMs and policy related to wider school information metrics. We provide new evidence and analyses which can be used to inform future revision of SPMs and their associated policies.

1. Research Questions

The evaluation and critique of the use of secondary school performance measures (SPMs) have been the subject of academic research throughout the three decades that they have formed part of the English educational system (Leckie & Goldstein, 2017; Levačić & Woods, 2002). They currently attract considerable attention within a wider debate around the suitability, effectiveness and effects of the existing school accountability system (House of Lords, 2023; House of Commons Education Committee, 2024). However, whilst increasing numbers of educational providers are collecting richer and richer data on education context, delivery and outcomes (Zhang, 2021), these data rarely contribute to the use of SPMs in a policy context. In this study we used empirical data and digital technologies to contribute to a novel assessment of the extent to which SPMs are meeting their stated policy goals. This analysis may then provide a basis for the evaluation of SPM design, their efficacy in providing a set of robust and accurate metrics which reliably capture school performance across a breadth of areas and their potential intended and unintended effects.

The research questions for this project are:

- How can we empirically identify and conceptualise any underlying latent constructs shaping 'performance' within SPMs?
- With reference to the current headline performance measures, what is the extent and breadth of the concept of 'performance'?
- To what extent do SPMs encapsulate elements beyond the influence of schools and can digital tools aid in assessing their influence on the stated policy goals of SPMs?

These analyses bring into question some important aspects of the existing SPM methodology, in terms of both the nature and breadth of the school characteristics, attributes, traits, qualities and quality which they encapsulate. In addition, this work provides some examples of how new technologies might be used with a range of empirical school-based data to evaluate, reimagine and redesign SPMs.

2. Research Methodology

The methods used in this work are exploratory factor analysis (EFA), confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), structural equation modelling (SEM), correlation analysis and agglomerative hierarchical clustering approaches.

2.1 Exploratory Factor Analysis

We first used exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to identify any latent constructs (or ‘factors’) underlying the set of metrics related to schools. We used the ‘psych’ and ‘lavaan’ R packages to do this.

The number of factors was identified using a range of techniques, including visual examination of scree plot, using Kaiser’s rule and the use of a parallel analysis scree plot (Figure 1.) and the outputs a PCA which we conducted using all 13 variables (Table 1.) suggested that there are either 3 or 4 latent variables which the 6 headline SPMs respond to.

The parallel scree plot (Figure 1) shows plots for three sets of data:

1. the real dataset being analysed,
2. a simulated dataset which was randomly generated to mimic the structure of the real dataset and so have a distribution of eigenvalues which that would be expected by chance (i.e., a distribution of eigenvalues which match the null hypothesis of there being no underlying factors in the data)
3. a resampled dataset made up of permutation samples from the real dataset.

There were eigenvalues of the factors from the actual data that were higher than those obtained from the simulated or resampled data (i.e., they exceeded the 95th percentile of the eigenvalue distribution from the simulated or resampled data). This indicated that the factors extracted from the actual data are likely meaningful and not simply due to chance. We used the point at which the eigenvalues from the actual data cross fall below the eigenvalue distribution from the simulated or resampled data to indicate the number of factors to retain. In this case it again indicated either 3 or 4 factors.

Table 1. Eigenvalues of the principal components arising from Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of the study dataset, indicating 3 principal components with eigenvalues greater than 1 (in green)

Principal Component	Eigenvalue
1	6.369
2	1.570
3	1.013
4	0.943
5	0.812
6	0.634
7	0.553
8	0.479
9	0.296
10	0.244
11	0.068
12	0.016
13	0.003

We conducted the EFA for the different numbers of factors in the range 2-5 and compared the fit measures (Comparative fit index (CFI), Tucker Lewis Index (TLI) and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)). These collectively suggested the use of 3 or 4 factors within the EFA.

We then ran a PCA to gain eigenvalues so that they could serve as a criterion for selecting the factors which capture the underlying structure of the data. The output of the PCA (table 1.), using the Kaiser Criterion (Kaiser, 1960), suggested 3 factors, with 3 principal components having eigenvalues above 1. However, there was also a 4th principal component with an eigenvalue very close to 1 (PC4 - 0.943). After running a 4 factor EFA we discovered that it resulted in a redundant factor (Factor 4) which had only very low factor loadings (Table 2). This therefore confirmed that 3 factors were most appropriate for this dataset.

Table 2. Factor loadings for 4 factor EFA using 6 headline SPM variables

	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4
Attain_8	0.679	0.515	0.308	0.417
Progress_8	0.368	0.837	0.251	0.137
Percent_EBacc_Entry	0.236	0.205	0.851	0.107
EBacc_APS	0.617	0.459	0.495	0.399
Basics	0.657	0.485	0.316	0.379
Destinations	0.609	0.215	0.18	0.000
	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4
SS loadings	1.836	1.5	1.259	0.51
Proportion Var	0.306	0.25	0.21	0.085
Cumulative Var	0.306	0.556	0.766	0.851

The EFA that we conducted for data related to all 3125 schools in the dataset and for the 6 headline performance measures, allowed us to explore (i) the relationships between these metrics and their underlying factors, and (ii) how they shape the concept of 'performance' within SPMs. We used varimax rotation in order to maximise the shared variance and so more specifically identify the factor upon which the data loaded.

2.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Structural Equation Modelling

We used confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and structural equation modelling (SEM) to explore and validate various models building on the findings of the EFA. These models had increasing levels of complexity in terms of the relationships between some or all of the manifest variables and factors.

CFA was first used to test and confirm the underlying factor structure for the set of 13 observed variables which was identified using the EFA techniques described above.

SEM was then used to extend the CFA by not only examining the relationships between observed variables and their underlying factors but also by allowing for the simultaneous examination of models which incorporated numerous latent variables, observed variables and various types of relationships (e.g., direct, indirect, mediating and/or moderating).

A series of models were developed using CFA/SEM outputs and fit measures, alongside theory related to school metrics, to consider the extent to which SPMs represent elements which are beyond the influence of schools. These techniques allowed us to further develop an understanding of the complex interplay of the underlying factors with the manifest variables and to extend our conceptualisation of the factors.

2.3 Correlation Analysis

We used correlation analysis, in the form of correlation matrices, to closely examine the associations between the 6 headline SPMs. This provided us with some important insights into both a) the conceptualisation, and b) the breadth and limitations of the concept of school 'performance' which is suggested by the selection of headline school metrics and the individual design of these metrics.

2.4 Cluster Analysis

Using agglomerative hierarchical clustering techniques, we further explored the patterns within the school information metrics and the extent and nature of their influence upon SPMs. While this type of analysis applied to school data is in its relatively early stages, and these techniques would require further development, testing, evaluation and refinement, there are clear indications that it could provide a valuable lens through which to view school metrics and so inform policy decisions in this area.

3. Data on Schools and Performance

All data for this study was sourced from the publicly available datasets via the UK Government website “Find and check the performance of schools and colleges in England”. This includes data for 3125 mainstream state secondary schools in England for the academic year 2021-2022.

We selected 13 variables from the data. These include the 6 headline performance measures and an additional 7 commonly used metrics of wider school information.

Headline performance measures:

Metric	Abbreviation used in this study
Attainment 8	Attain_8
Progress 8	Progress_8
% grade 5+ in English and maths ('Basics')	Basics
%EBacc entry	Percent_EBacc_Entry
EBacc Average Point Score	EBacc_APS
Pupil destinations	Destinations

These are designated by the Department for Education (DfE) as ‘headline performance measures’ to establish their greater importance regarding school accountability and to provide a basis for year-on-year comparison. They are selected and designed to provide an overview of school effectiveness, with a focus on student progress, attainment, curriculum breadth and post-16 transitions to education, employment or training. They are intended to enable a range of stakeholders to assess school performance, identify areas for improvement and support informed decision-making regarding education policy, school choice, and resource allocation.

Wider school information metrics:

Metric	Abbreviation used in this study
KS2 Average Point Score	KS2_APS
% of pupils with Free School Meals ever in last six years	FSM6
% English as additional language	EAL
% Special educational needs	SEN
school admission policy (selective or non-selective)	Selective
Whether the school has a religious character	Religious_Char
School gender of entry (mixed or single gender)	Single_Gender

These are the key items of information about nature of schools and their intake included within the dataset. They are the main features and metrics related to schools and their student cohorts which are used to inform the context in which the school is working. They feature as key items of wider information about schools which are used alongside school performance data in a wide range of settings, for example DfE Statistical First Releases, the DfE’s “Compare school and college performance in England” and “Get Information about Schools” website, Ofsted Inspection Data Summary Reports and school inspection reports.

4. Key Findings

4.1 Factor Analysis

Table 3. Factor loadings for 3 factor EFA using only the 6 headline SPM variables.

	Attainment (+ Destinations)	Progress	Curriculum
Attain_8	0.857	0.413	0.299
Progress_8	0.456	0.854	0.239
Percent_EBacc_Entry	0.291	0.183	0.831
EBacc_APS	0.783	0.37	0.491
Basics	0.819	0.389	0.307
Destinations	0.548	0.192	0.182
	MR1	MR3	MR2
SS loadings	2.612	1.259	1.205
Proportion Var	0.435	0.21	0.201
Cumulative Var	0.435	0.645	0.846

Figure 2. Factor Analysis Diagram showing factor loadings for EFA using only the 6 headline SPM variables.

These latent variables can be conceptualised to be:

- Factor 1 = '**Attainment (+ Destinations)**' - Attainment 8, Basics, EBacc APS and Destinations
- Factor 2 = '**Progress**' - Progress 8
- Factor 3 = '**Curriculum**' - % EBacc entry

'Destinations' has a significantly lower factor loading than the other performance measures, suggesting only a moderate correlation with any of the underlying factors. While this could itself suggest some degree of breadth in the overall collection of headline performance metrics, it should be noted that Destinations did not load more strongly to another, fourth factor. This might be explained in number of ways. First, the destinations measure is actually based on the previous academic year's cohort of students. There therefore may have been some significant statistical fluctuations associated around this, based around the individual students' interests, aspirations, influences and opportunities. The mean student cohort size for the dataset used here was 177, meaning that the sample size from year to year was relatively small and would be unlikely to statistically smooth such variation. Second, it may suggest the presence of other variables, some of which are beyond the influence of the school (e.g., availability of employment, education and training in the school's locality) which are not included in the current model. The impact of such contextual variables, which are outside the schools' sphere of influence, on the headline SPMs is a theme that we will return to again below. This may suggest that other sources of data, related to these variables, could be incorporated into a more complex and sophisticated model, allowing them to be incorporated to facilitate more data-informed policy. There is some potential to extend this study and to explore subsets of this dataset, looking at groups of schools by the characteristics indicated by the school information metrics, or using data related to geography, for example, to examine whether a higher proportion of the variance in Destinations, or the other variables, is explained.

Perhaps the most significant finding from the Exploratory Factor Analysis was that 3 out of the 6 headline school performance measures (Attainment 8, Basics and EBacc APS) load strongly onto just one factor. This suggests that these 3 school performance metrics are representing the same latent variable i.e., the same feature of the school's 'performance', that of 'attainment'. This implies a degree of redundancy in the 4 headline SPMs which respond to Factor 1 ('Attainment + Destinations') and therefore limitations to the breadth of 'performance' as currently captured in the published metrics.

Building upon the insights gained from the EFA, we used the CFA/SEM approach described above to identify, conceptualise, examine and further develop several factors related to school performance data and data related to wider school information. These included factors which were conceptualised as 'Performance', 'Attainment', 'School Context', 'School Character', 'Progress', 'Curriculum' and 'Destinations'. These factors can provide a valuable basis on which to evaluate policy around school accountability, the interpretation of SPMs and the complex meanings and values which they represent. This analysis provides greater insight into the underlying latent variables for SPMs and wider school information and moves toward a better understanding of the complex relationships between these latent variables and the published metrics. This is important, both in identifying the impact of factors which would not typically be classified as 'performance' on SPMs (and are, in the most part, outside the influence of schools) and in suggesting potential mechanisms to address such issues.

We used a set of model fit indices (Table 4.) to evaluate, compare, modify, refine and validate a series of new and increasingly complex models and the relationships between the manifest and latent variables that they represented.

Table 4. Model fit indices used in CFA/SEM analysis and development of models

Model fit index	Acceptable value for the purpose of this study	Notes
Goodness of fit index (GFI)	A value greater than 0.90	Simulation studies (Cho et al., 2020; Sivo et al., 2006) suggest that the GFI can effectively distinguish between correct and mis-specified models with a cut-off value of 0.9
Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI), also known as the Tucker Lewis index (TLI)	A value greater than 0.95	Hu and Bentler (1999) have suggested $NNFI \geq 0.95$ as pointing towards good fit
Comparative fit index (CFI)	A value greater than 0.90	Studies have shown that a value greater than 0.90 (e.g., $CFI \geq 0.95$) is needed in order to ensure that mis-specified models are not accepted (Hu and Bentler, 1999)
root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA)	Value Less than 0.10	Browne and Cudeck (1993) recommended that $RMSEA \leq 0.05$ would indicate a close fit of the model in relation to the degrees of freedom," and Hu and Bentler (1999) suggested that an RMSEA smaller than .06 and a CFI and TLI larger than .95 indicate relatively good model–data fit in general

There is agreement that researchers using structural equation modelling require some tools to allow them to evaluate the extent to which a model fits the sample data (Sivo et al., 2006). Many different fit indices have been developed. However, each of these indices addresses a different feature of ‘model suitability’, such as parsimony, effects of sample size and comparisons to null models, as well as lacking directly comparable scales or distributions. It is for these reasons that Cudeck and Henly (1991) argue that any judgement of model fit will always have some degree of statistical decision making which cannot be simply reduced to thresholds. While fixed cut-off values for goodness of fit indices continue to be widely used in a range of applied research areas, this is the subject of some controversy. Research continues into the use of such indices in this way and innovative approaches are being developed to aid in the determination of model fit (Groskurth, Bluemke & Lechner, 2023; Beribisky & Cribbie, 2024), arguing for a move away from the rigid use of absolute goodness-of-fit cut-off thresholds to a more nuanced application of such metrics in a variety of research scenarios. A full consideration of this question is beyond the scope of this project. However, it is worth acknowledging our approach to the use of fit indices here. First, in line with common practice in this field (Kyndt & Onghena, 2014) and in line with the influential work of Hu and Bentler (1999) we used four different fit indices, to provide breadth in our consideration of model fit and to allow for the differing sensitivities of the metrics to a range of model and sample features. Second, the fit measures were used to compare the adaptations to models to previous versions, rather than to accept or reject

models based on cut-offs, as we iteratively developed the models, gaining insights into the complex interaction of variables and latent factors. Finally, while we have stated ‘acceptable values’ for the fit measures used in this study above, we also acknowledge that at best these can only provide a ‘rule of thumb’ for model fit. This work seeks to adopt an innovative approach to the consideration of SPMs by revealing, through the analysis of latent variables, which features of schools, whether ‘performance’, ‘context’ and/or ‘character’, SPMs are responding to. However, even in the final model presented here (Model B) one of the fit measures, RMSEA, falls slightly below the accepted cut-off for this index (0.103 compared to an acceptable value of less than 0.1). This speaks both of progress made in this study and of potential further research to explore these ideas in greater depth.

4.1.1 Performance (‘perform’)

Performance Model 1

Figure 3. Model diagram for Performance Model 1.

Table 4. Model fit indices for Attainment Model 1.

GFI	NNFI	CFI	RMSEA
0.824	0.813	0.888	0.321

Performance Model 2

Figure 4. Model diagram for Performance Model 1.

Table 5. Model fit indices for Attainment Model 1.

GFI	NNFI	CFI	RMSEA
0.793	0.764	0.882	0.43

The model fit indices for both ‘performance’ models 1 and 2 indicate an insufficiently strong model fit. In Performance Model 1 ‘performance’ was modelled as including all 6 of the current headline SPMs. For Performance Model 2 the ‘Destinations’ variable, which had the lowest factor loading in Performance Model 1, was removed. This did nothing to improve the model fit, with all fit measures indicating that the inclusion of ‘Destinations’ improved the fit of the model to the data.

The next step, building on the output of the EFA (Table 2. and Figure 2.), was to examine models for the latent variable for ‘Attainment’ suggested there.

4.1.2 Attainment (‘attain’)

Attainment Model 1

Figure 5. Model diagram for Attainment Model 1.

Table 6. Model fit indices for Attainment Model 1.

GFI	NNFI	CFI	RMSEA
0.994	0.995	0.998	0.072

Attainment Model 2

Figure 6. Model diagram for Attainment Model 2.

Table 7. Model fit indices for Attainment Model 2.

GFI	NNFI	CFI	RMSEA
1	1	1	0

The fit indices for Attainment Model 1 suggest a good level of fit. Despite this fact, the factor loading for ‘Destination’ remains relatively low for this model, at 0.63. When ‘Destinations’ is removed from this model to form Attainment Model 2 we are unable to use the model fit indices (as they now suggest a ‘perfect’ fit). This model, a one factor/three items default marker model, has zero degrees of freedom. It is saturated. This is a consequence of having the same number of parameters as the size of the variance-covariance matrix. The fit measures are typically a comparison between a larger, less parsimonious, covariance matrix and a smaller latent variable solution. Since for this model, and others I encounter, they are the same size, the fit will always be indicated as perfect. It should be emphasised that this does not, in itself, indicate a fundamental problem with the model. However, the relationship between these three variables as a latent variable (‘attain’) is equivalent in complexity to modelling the covariance between them. This means that the model ‘fit’ is not a better statistical representation of the data. Nevertheless, the latent factor is a more useful representation as indicated by the very high factor loadings. This indicates that this combination of Attain_8, Basics and the EBacc_APS together constitute a very strong model for measuring ‘Attainment’. Crucially, however, it also brings into question whether it is either necessary or appropriate to use half of the 6 current headline school performance measures to measure this single latent variable, when one metric might have been sufficient, and why this specific aspect of school performance has been prioritised over others within the current and, it could be argued, previous sets of headline performance measures. This question becomes all the more important following the announcement by the Department for Education (2024) that no Progress 8 measures will be published for 2024/25 and 2025/26 as a consequence of the cancellation of primary tests and assessment in 2019/20 and 2020/21 due to disruption caused by COVID-19. Three of the remaining 5 metrics realistically reflect the exact same aspect of school ‘performance’, and so the breadth of the concept of school ‘performance’ is further constrained.

The wider school information metrics can be separated into two distinct categories. First there are metrics which are measures of the schools’ pupil populations. These are the continuous variables of KS2_APS, FSM6, EAL and SEN which for the purpose of this study we defined as ‘school context’. Second there are those metrics which are associated with what can be described as the character of the school rather than its cohort of students. These are the binary variables of Selective, Religious_Char and Single_Gender which are defined here as ‘school character’.

Next, we examined models for school context, before turning our attention to measures of school character.

4.1.3 School Context (‘context’)

School Context Model 1

Figure 7. Model diagram for School Context Model 1.

Table 8. Model fit indices for School Context Model 1.

GFI	NNFI	CFI	RMSEA
0.946	0.601	0.867	0.233

School Context Model 2

Figure 8. Model diagram for School Context Model 2.

Table 9. Model fit indices for School Context Model 2.

GFI	NNFI	CFI	RMSEA
1	1	1	0

School Context Model 3

Figure 9. Model diagram for School Context Model 3.

Table 10. Model fit indices for School Context Model 3.

GFI	NNFI	CFI	RMSEA
1	1	1	0

We began with a model for school context which included all four continuous variables associated with this latent variable (School Context Model 1, Fig 7.). While the GFI for this model (0.946) suggested a good model fit, the other model fit indices brought into question some aspects of the model. This, combined with the relatively low factor loadings for two variables, SEN and EAL, prompted the testing of two further models, School Context Model 2 (Fig 8.) which omitted SEN and School Context Model 3 (Fig 9.) which did

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not include EAL. Both of these models were saturated, meaning the model fit indices were not useful in the judgement of the model, and instead attention needed to be paid to the factor loadings. Here we see that the factor loadings for both SEN and EAL within these models are relatively low. One possible explanation for this is the very nature of these variables. SEN, the percentage of students with a special education need, does not, on its own, give a clear indication of the implication of this for a school and its students with regard to potential consequences for the school's SPMs. That would largely depend upon the nature, complexity and the severity of the needs of individual students, which are not indicated by this variable. Similarly, the variable for percentage of students who have English as additional language, does not provide any direct indication of the effect of this for the school. Other factors would affect this, including, for example, length of residency in England, individual student's English ability, first language as well as an interaction with other factors e.g., ethnicity, socio-economic disadvantage or special educational needs (Strand, Malmberg & Hall, 2015). These data are, on the whole, currently routinely collected through standard school census returns and made available as part of the National Pupil Database e.g., SEN provision, language, ethnicity, Income Deprivation Affecting Children Indices (IDACI), length of residency in England (which can be deduced from the available data). However, any analysis which sought to fully incorporate these data into the production of school performance metrics, including the interactions of these various factors together, would require the utilisation of such data at a student level. Whether the cost of this far more granular approach to the processing of school data would be justified in terms of its potential benefits would need to be the subject of further study. However, the constant and rapid advances in computational approaches, in terms of processing power, innovative methodologies and volumes of data, for example, make such a prospect increasingly feasible.

A combination of the two variables FSM6 and KS2_APS is therefore judged to be a better representation of the latent factor 'school context' (Fig 10.).

Figure 10. Final model for School Context

4.1.4 School Character ('school_char')

Figure 11. Model diagram for initial School Character Model.

Table 11. Model fit indices for School Context Model.

GFI	NNFI	CFI	RMSEA
1	1	1	0

The model for school character was made up of the three variables associated with this feature of schools, Religious_Char, Single_Gender and Selective. Since it was another example of a one factor/three items default marker model it has there are zero degrees of freedom, i.e., it is saturated. Using the factor loadings, we can see that Religious_Char has by far the lowest factor loading. There is evidence to suggest that whether a school has a religious character is not sufficient to indicate implications for schools output data, as represented in SPMs (Andrews & Johnes, 2016). To address this, it would be necessary to consider factors including the specific nature of the religious character, the communities served and interactions with other features for the school e.g., levels of deprivation and special educational needs. While these data are available, they are currently self-reported by schools and published in the Department for Education's 'Get Information About Schools' website. There is some indication that the information held there for some schools is unreliable, perhaps due in part to the fact that these data are not widely referred to, and it would therefore require far greater scrutiny and validation before it was possible for it to be used in the context of creating SPMs. As it is, there is not as clear a direct association between the binary variable of Religious_Char (whether a school has a religious character or not) and school performance metrics as there is for other metrics of wider school information. Religious_Char was therefore removed, leaving 'school character' represented by a combination of the two remaining variables, Single_Gender and Selective (Fig 12.).

Figure 12. Final model for School Character

4.1.5 Development of models

We used the final six factor models ('school character', 'school context', 'attainment', 'destinations', 'curriculum' and 'progress') to construct a series of models using a structural equation modelling approach. This provided us with a framework with which to estimate the strength and significance of the complex relationships between the latent factors and manifest variables and to assess model fit in order to iteratively adapt and refine the model.

We began with a model which included all of the final models for these six factors, with each of the 'performance' factors ('attainment', 'destinations', 'curriculum' and 'progress') regressed on both 'school character' and 'school context'. In addition, it included 'school context' regressed on 'school character'. This was designed to begin to explore the relationships between those factors associated with school 'performance' with those which related to the character of the schools and the features of the schools' student cohorts (Fig. 13).

Figure 13. SPM Model 1 – initial SEM model incorporating all four SPM factors as responding to both 'school character' and 'school context' factors and 'school context' responding to 'school character'

Table 12. Model fit indices for SPM Model 1.

GFI	NNFI	CFI	RMSEA
0.727	0.571	0.687	0.287

Two things were evident from the output of this model. First, the fit measures for SPM Model 1 (Table 12.) do not indicate a strong model fit. Therefore, while this model may have proved to be a useful starting point, further work was necessary to iteratively move towards a model with a fit to the data which was satisfactory. Second, there were some factor loadings within this model with very low values. In particular, the factor loading for 'school character' on 'attainment' (0.04) and 'curriculum' (-0.03). Therefore, for the next model, SPM Model 2, we used SPM Model 1 as a starting point but had the regressions of 'attainment' and 'curriculum' on 'school character' removed (Fig. 14.).

Figure 14. SPM Model 2 – SEM model incorporating all four SPM factors as responding to ‘school context’ and only ‘destinations’, ‘curriculum’ and ‘school context’ responding to ‘school character’

Table 13. Model fit indices for SPM Model 1.

GFI	NNFI	CFI	RMSEA
0.840	0.831	0.906	0.232

The fit measures for SPM Model 2 (Table 13.) were stronger than those for SPM Model 1 but still did not indicate a good model fit. We used the same strategy as employed in the last iteration by identifying the lowest factor loadings and then removing them from the model. These were between ‘school character’ and ‘destinations’ (-0.33) and ‘school character’ and ‘curriculum’ (0.06), and so these regressions were then removed from SPM Model 2 to form Model A (Fig 13.). Model A had stronger fit measures (Table 13.) compared to its predecessor and was more parsimonious. This suggested that, for this dataset, ‘school character’, as defined by whether a school is single gender and/or whether it has a selective admissions policy, had a strong influence upon the features of schools’ student bodies (with a factor loading of 0.83), in particular the average prior attainment of students at the end of key stage 2 (KS2_APS) and the proportion of students who are disadvantaged, as indicated by the proportion who have been eligible for free school meals at some point in the last six years (FSM6).

Model B was a further refinement of Model A, which allowed us to focus only on attainment within the 4 ‘performance’ factors. This indicated a very good model fit, with only RMSEA narrowly higher than the suggested value for a good model fit (Table 15.). This suggested that whether schools were single gender and whether they had a selective admissions policy (here captured as the single factor, ‘school character’) had a significant impact upon both the levels of prior attainment and proportion of disadvantage for schools’ student bodies (i.e., ‘school context’). These, in turn, were strong indicators of the school ‘performance’ as denoted by ‘destinations’, ‘progress’ and ‘curriculum’ and were very strong indicators of the ‘performance’ factor ‘attainment’. Crucially, what we could see here were factors which were beyond the influence of the school provision having a very strong impact on the metrics currently being used as indicators of school ‘performance’. It would appear, therefore that SPMs may well be measuring something meaningful about the schools. However, given that the factors described here as ‘school character’ and ‘school context’ have no direct, obvious relationship to the quality of school provision, it seriously brings into question the extent to which the metrics currently forming the 6 headline SPMs are actually measuring school ‘performance’. This is important as SPMs are intended to act as proxies for school effectiveness in informing parental choice, inspection, interventions and school improvement planning.

Figure 15. Model A - final model incorporating latent variables of 'school character' and 'school context' and all four SPM latent variables ('attainment', 'destinations', 'curriculum' and 'progress')

Table 14. Model fit indices for Model A.

GFI	NNFI	CFI	RMSEA
0.831	0.839	0.904	0.226

Figure 16. Model B - final model incorporating latent variables of 'school character' and 'school context' and only 'attainment' SPM latent variables

Table 15. Model fit indices for Model B.

GFI	NNFI	CFI	RMSEA
0.964	0.973	0.985	0.103

This all suggests further research which could be carried out to explore this in greater depth. Some of the questions which might be addressed are:

- Are there indirect associations between the indicators of ‘school character’ (single gender and selective) and high-quality teaching, and, if so, what might be the reasons behind that?
- If all the current headline SPMs are strongly influenced by factors which are beyond the scope of school ‘performance’ (in particular, prior attainment and levels of disadvantage), what, if anything, can be done to adjust for this, to ensure the published measures are meaningful, useful, fair and accurate?

4.2 Correlation analysis

Correlation analysis revealed further extremely strong associations between Attainment 8, Basics and EBacc APS (figure 17.) as indicated in the previous analysis. While this is relatively unsurprising given the common basis of each of these metrics, it is the strength of this correlation (Table 13) which is significant.

Figure 17. Correlation matrix of all headline current headline SPMs.

Table 16. Correlation between Attainment 8, EBacc APS and ‘Basics’ SPMs.

Headline SPMs		Correlation
Attainment 8	EBacc Average Points Score	0.974
Attainment 8	% grade 5+ in English and maths (‘Basics’)	0.947
% grade 5+ in English and maths (‘Basics’)	EBacc Average Points Score	0.936

Just as we had seen in the 3-factor exploratory factor analysis above, the strong correlation between these three headline SPMs indicated a substantial narrowing of the concept of ‘performance’ within the 6 headline SPMs. In turn this might suggest some degree of scope for policy to replace one or two of these measures with alternative measures. This would retain the focus on performance in a core of academic subjects, including English and maths, while also introducing greater breadth to the concept of school ‘performance’.

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4.3 Cluster Analysis

We conducted agglomerative hierarchical clustering analysis with the 3125 mainstream state secondary schools in England using the 7 variables related to wider school information. The output of this can be seen in the cluster dendrogram, Figure 18.

Figure 18. Cluster Dendrogram of hierarchical clustering analysis of entire dataset using ward D method (which uses the sum of squared distances as the criterion to minimize when merging clusters)

4 clusters were identified. In line with hierarchical clustering methodology, this could be adjusted, to form more or less clusters. 4 clusters were chosen in this instance as the parallel scree plot (figure 19), using the result of a PCA, showed variances for each principal component suggesting an elbow between 3 or 4 and the point that the eigenvalues from the actual data cross fell below the eigenvalue distribution from the simulated and resampled data was also 4. In addition, the % of variance explained by 4 dimensions was satisfactory at 92.3% (figure 20). Finally, a silhouette width plot (figure 21) identified 4 as the optimal number of clusters.

Figure 19. Parallel scree plot

Figure 20. Percentage of variance explained by each dimension

Figure 21. Average silhouette width plot indicating optimal number of clusters to be 4

Table 17. Number of schools in each cluster.

Cluster	1	2	3	4
Number of schools	1415	1292	255	163

Next, we gathered the mean score for each cluster and for each variable for further analysis and interpretation (table 18.)

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	<i>mean</i>
KS2_APS	102.15	104.78	102.14	112.75	103.79
FSM6	34.32	17.44	41.93	6.98	26.54
EAL	13.28	10.79	66.28	16.35	16.74
SEN	18.17	11.67	13.53	6.16	14.48
Selective	0.00	0.15	0.00	98.77	5.22
Religious_Char	51.24	54.64	49.41	83.44	54.18
Single_Gender	2.19	11.92	20.00	71.17	11.26
Attain_8	43.85	52.65	48.88	74.19	49.48
Progress_8	-0.25	0.13	0.26	0.57	-0.01
Percent_EBacc_Entry	29.37	42.26	50.95	77.70	38.98
EBacc_APS	3.73	4.64	4.38	6.99	4.33
Basics	39.05	56.79	50.21	94.01	50.16
Destinations	91.92	95.58	92.44	99.06	93.85

Table 18. Mean value of each variable for clusters 1 to 4

This suggests 4 clusters with distinct characteristics:

Cluster 1 (n=1415)

The schools in this cluster, in general, have:

students with lower than national average prior attainment (mean KS2 APS is 102.15 compared to the national mean by school of 103.79)

higher than average percentages of students from disadvantaged backgrounds (mean FSM6 is almost 8% higher than the national mean of 26.5%)

slightly lower than average percentages of students with English as an additional language (mean EAL for schools in this cluster is 13.3% compared to 16.7% nationally)

higher than average percentages of students with special educational needs (mean SEN is over 18%, 3.7% higher than the national figure)

Generally, they:

are **non-selective** (no schools in cluster 1 are selective in their admissions policy), **very slightly less likely to have religious character** (51% of schools in cluster 1 compared to 54% nationally) and **much less likely to be single gender schools** (only 2% of schools are single gender, compared to a national figure of 11%).

With regard to headline school performance measures, they are generally **below average for all 6 metrics**.

Schools in this cluster have a mean **Attainment 8 value which is 5.63 below the national mean score**. This equates to **students, on average, attaining a quarter of a grade below students nationally with similar prior attainments** across the 8 subjects included in these measures (mean Progress 8 is -0.25).

The mean **percentage of students entered for the EBacc is nearly 10% less than the national average** of 39%.

The **mean Ebacc Average Points Score is the equivalent of over half a grade below national** (EBacc APS of 3.73 compared to the national figure of 4.33) and, on average, the **percentage of students gaining grade 5 or above in English and Maths is 11% lower than the national value** of 50%.

The **percentage of pupils continuing to a sustained education, apprenticeship or employment destination for this cluster is 2% lower than the national mean** of 93.9%.

Cluster 2 (n = 1292)

The schools in this cluster, in general, have:

students with above national average prior attainment (mean KS2 APS is 104.78 compared to the national mean by school of 103.79)

below average percentages of students from disadvantaged backgrounds (mean FSM6 is almost 9% lower than the national mean of 26.5%)

lower than average percentages of students with English as an additional language (mean EAL for schools in this cluster is 10.8% compared to 16.7% nationally)

below average percentages of students with special educational needs (mean SEN is over 11.7%, 2.8% lower than the national figure)

Generally, they:

are **non-selective** (only 2 schools in cluster 2 are selective in their admissions policy), **as likely to have religious character and to be single gender as all schools nationally.**

With regard to headline school performance measures, they are generally **above average for all 6 metrics.**

Schools in this cluster have a mean **Attainment 8 value which is 3.17 above the national mean score.**

The mean Progress 8 score for cluster 2 schools is 0.13, meaning that their students, **on average attain just over one eighth of a grade higher than their peers with similar prior attainment in each of the subjects included in the Progress 8 calculation.**

The mean **percentage of students entered for the EBacc is slightly higher than the national average** of 39% (cluster 2 % Ebacc Entry = 42.3%).

The **mean Ebacc Average Points Score is the equivalent of just less than a third of a grade above national** (EBacc APS of 4.64 compared to the national figure of 4.33) and, on average, the **percentage of students gaining grade 5 or above in English and Maths is 6.6% higher than the national value** of 50%.

The **percentage of pupils continuing to a sustained education, apprenticeship or employment destination for this cluster is 1.7% higher than the national mean** of 93.9%.

Cluster 3 (n = 255)

The schools in this cluster, in general, have:

students with lower than national average prior attainment (mean KS2 APS is 102.14 compared to the national mean by school of 103.79)

above average percentages of students from disadvantaged backgrounds (mean FSM6 is almost 15.4% higher than the national mean of 26.5%)

significantly higher than average percentages of students with English as an additional language (mean EAL for schools in this cluster is 66.3% compared to 16.7% nationally)

slightly below average percentages of students with special educational needs (mean SEN is 13.5%, 0.94% lower than the national figure)

Generally, they:

are **non-selective** (no schools in cluster 3 are selective in their admissions policy), **slightly less likely to have religious character** (49.4% of schools have religious character compared to 54.2% nationally) **and more likely to be single gender** (20% of schools are single gender compared to 11.3% of all schools nationally).

With regard to headline school performance measures, they present a **more complex picture, being generally above average for 4 of the metrics, and below average for the remaining 2.**

Schools in this cluster have a mean **Attainment 8 value which is slightly below the national mean score** (48.9 compared to 49.5 nationally). This equates to **students, on average, attaining a quarter of a grade higher than students nationally with similar prior attainment** across the 8 subjects included in these measures (mean Progress 8 is 0.26).

The mean **percentage of students entered for the EBacc is significantly higher than the national average** of 39% (% Ebacc Entry for cluster 3 is 50.1%).

The **mean Ebacc Average Points Score is very close to the national average** (EBacc APS of 4.38 compared to the national figure of 4.33) and, on average, the **percentage of students gaining grade 5 or above in English and Maths is also very close to the national value** of 50%.

The **percentage of pupils continuing to a sustained education, apprenticeship or employment destination for this cluster is 1.4% lower than the national mean** of 93.9%.

Cluster 4 (n = 163)

The schools in this cluster, in general, have:

students with significantly higher than national average prior attainment (mean KS2 APS is 112.75 compared to the national mean by school of 103.79)

significantly below average percentages of students from disadvantaged backgrounds (mean FSM6 is almost 20% lower than the national mean of 26.5%, with only 7% of students classed as disadvantaged).

around average percentages of students with English as an additional language (mean EAL for schools in this cluster is 16.4% compared to 16.7% nationally)

significantly below average percentages of students with special educational needs (mean SEN is 6.2%, 8.3% lower than the national figure)

Generally, they:

are **selective** (161 of the 163 schools in cluster 4 are selective in their admissions policy), **significantly more likely to have religious character** (83.4% of schools have religious character compared to 54.2% nationally) **and more likely to be single gender** (71% of schools are single gender compared to 11.3% of all schools nationally).

With regard to headline school performance measures, they are generally **significantly above average for all 6 metrics**.

Schools in this cluster have a mean **Attainment 8 value which is well above the national mean score** (74.2 compared to 49.5 nationally). This equates to **students, on average, attaining over half of a grade higher than students nationally with similar prior attainment** in each of the 8 subjects included in these measures (mean Progress 8 is 0.57).

The mean **percentage of students entered for the EBacc is double the national average** of 39% (cluster 4 % Ebacc Entry = 78%).

The **mean Ebacc Average Points Score is significantly above national average** (EBacc APS of 7.00 compared to the national figure of 4.33).

On average, the **percentage of students gaining grade 5 or above in English and Maths (94%) is also very much higher than the national value** of 50%.

The **percentage of pupils continuing to a sustained education, apprenticeship or employment destination for this cluster is 99.1%, which is higher than the national mean** of 93.9%.

Figure 19. Plots (boxplots and stacked bar charts) of the distributions of mean scaled values of the 7 'wider school information' variables for clusters 1 to 4.

We created visualisations of the distributions of all of the 13 variables across the 4 clusters using boxplots (figures 19 and 20). These included crucial information about the range, the median, the inter-quartile range and any outliers and summarise visually the differences in the clusters, so aiding in their interpretation.

Figure 20. Boxplots of the distributions of mean scaled values of the 6 SPM variables for clusters 1 to 4.

We created an additional radar plot visualisation of the clusters (figure 21.). This could be used to both illustrate the complex interplay of the variables in each of the four clusters as well as providing a means of identifying their distinguishing features, both in terms of the school information variables which were used to create them and in the SPMs for schools in each cluster.

Figure 21. Radar plot of the mean scaled values for each of the 13 variables for Cluster 1 -4 formed using hierarchical clustering of the 7 school information variables.

We then used a range of approaches to evaluate the quality of the clusters in this analysis.

The average silhouette width was found to be 0.21. Since this is a measure of how similar each point is to its own cluster compared to other clusters, this, on its own, might suggest that there is no substantial structure in the clustering. The silhouette plot (figure 22.) also suggested some potential issues with assignment in cluster 1 and, to a lesser extent, cluster 2, with significant numbers of schools with negative silhouette coefficients.

Figure 22. Silhouette Plot for agglomerative hierarchical clustering using Ward's minimum variance method for all English state schools and based on the 7 variables of 'wider school information'.

The Dunn Index, which measures the ratio of the smallest distance between observations not in the same cluster to the largest intra-cluster distance, was relatively low at 0.01733. This again suggested that clusters may not have been very separated or compact.

However, the Calinski–Harabasz index indicated a relatively high value (890). This suggested, contrary to the other metrics above, that the clusters are both compact within themselves and also distinct from one another.

Finally, we used t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbour Embedding (t-SNE) as a method of dimension reduction and then visualization. The t-SNE visualisation (figure 23.) suggests some degree of distinct structure for the four clusters generated by agglomerative hierarchical clustering. At the same time, it raised some potential questions around the structure of cluster 2.

These different approaches to clustering evaluation did not provide us with a consistent assessment of the quality of the clusters formed. We therefore needed to accept that, while this analysis suggests some potential in the use of these clustering techniques to further explore the relationships between SPMs and wider school 'character' and 'context' metrics, further work would be required to refine and evaluate these techniques. We will return to a discussion of the limitations of these clustering evaluation approaches below.

Figure 23. t_SNE Visualisation for agglomerative hierarchical clustering using Ward's minimum variance method for all English state schools and based on the 7 variables of 'wider school information'.

5. Discussion

The future of the English school accountability system is currently the subject of increased attention. This can be seen, for example, in the inquiry conducted by the Education Select Committee (House of Commons Education Committee, 2024) into Ofsted's work with schools, the calls for change to the inspection system by all main teaching unions (Adams, 2023) and the Labour Party's commitment to introduce a School Report Card (Schools Week, 2023) which forms part of their campaign in the lead up to the 2024 general election. The announcement from the DfE that Progress 8 would neither be included nor replaced in the published SPMs for 2025 and 2026 has also contributed to the discourse around the effectiveness and effects of SPMs.

The purpose of this study was to assess the extent to which secondary SPMs in England are meeting their policy objectives. In particular, we set out to use empirical data to first identify and then conceptualise the underlying latent constructs which shape SPMs. In doing this we sought to gain some insight into the breadth of the concept of 'performance' as captured by the existing 6 headline SPMs and the extent to which they represent aspects of schools which are not directly related to the quality of the educational provision and, consequently, would not reasonably be classified as features of school 'performance'.

5.1 Constructs underlying headline SPMs

The factor analysis that we conducted provided insight into the conceptualisation of 'performance' within the existing 6 headline school performance measures. Using EFA, we found that the 6 headline SPMs suggest neither a single common, consistent latent variable nor 6 broad factors of performance. Instead, using CFA, we showed that the 6 headline SPMs are actually shaped by 4 latent variables, each capturing a different priority aspect of the work of schools: 'attainment', 'progress', 'curriculum' and 'destinations'. This is important for three reasons.

First, it provides us with some clarity into the conceptualisation of 'performance' as captured by the existing 6 headline SPMs. Even if we assume that not all metrics are treated, in their interpretation, with equal priority, this could be considered to communicate a particular emphasis on 'attainment' over the other latent variables, since this is represented by 3 out of the 6 headline SPMs.

Second, while Progress 8 may, in practice, be more widely to have been considered a 'fairer' measure of performance (Education Policy Institute, 2018) and as a consequence afforded greater emphasis (TES, 2024), the absence of this measure in the published SPMs for 2025 and 2026 (Department for Education, 2024) with no alternative replacement metric, will only serve to place greater priority on the remaining 5 SPMs and their associated 3 latent variables of 'attainment', 'curriculum' and 'destinations'.

Finally, as we discuss next, 'attainment' is the latent variable which is especially strongly influenced by school 'context' and 'character', factors which are beyond the direct influence of schools, and so more weakly captures the aspects of quality of educational provision, the features of schools which 'performance' measures are expected to capture.

5.2 Wider information about schools impacts headline SPMs

CFA provided us with opportunities to explore the school metrics related to wider information around schools' characters as well as the contexts in which schools work. Two further latent variables were conceptualised in this analysis; 'school character' and 'school context'. Using SEM we examined, and iteratively refined, models to more deeply explore the relationships between the 4 performance factors and 'school character' and 'school context'. Notably, this shows us that these factors, which lie beyond the direct, day to day influence of the work of schools, have a strong impact on the 6 headline SPMs and that this is particularly strong for the three SPMs which are indicators of 'attainment'. This raises important

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questions about the extent to which the existing headline school 'performance' measures are effective in capturing and representing school 'performance', i.e., acting as proxies for school effectiveness and the quality of education provided by the school. These questions may then be intensified further by the Progress 8 gap in SPMs for 2025 and 2026.

5.3 The breadth of headline SPMs

Correlation analysis provided us with further insight into the nature of the relationships between SPMs. Of particular note is that it quantified the extremely strong correlation between 3 variables; Attainment 8, EBacc Average Points Score and the 'Basics' measure. This prompts questions as to why the existing headline SPMs include 3 metrics which such a high correlation that we can reasonably conclude that they are effectively measures of the same thing. This may simply be an indication of an intentional priority being given to attainment within the headline SPMs. However, this raises two questions.

First, there is considerable acceptance that Progress 8 may be considered to be the priority SPM. In the main part this is due to it controlling for the prior attainment of students at a school and so providing a fairer basis upon which to judge the quality of school examination performance. In terms of their interpretation, and the wider discourse around a school's SPMs, Progress 8 may well then be seen to be given greater priority than the other 5 SPMs. However, at the same time this seems to be at odds with a collection of 6 headline SPMS, half of which are measures of attainment, not progress. This is especially significant in light of the announcement by the Department for Education, due to keystone 2 assessment disruption during the COVID-19 pandemic, that Progress 8 will not form part of the published headline SPMs for 2025 and 2026.

Second, based on the findings here that SPMs are being so strongly impacted by factors which are measures of school 'character' and 'context' rather than performance, it would seem that there would be scope, from a policy point of view, to replace two of the three highly correlated metrics with alternative measures which are better designed to capture the quality of the provision at a school, which might also seek to control for the differences in character and context.

5.4 Data-driven analysis of schools can inform SPM review

The cluster analysis that we conducted demonstrated the potential of this technique in identifying differences between schools, their characters, contexts, communities and, significantly, the challenges which they face. More work would certainly need to be done on this before it could be reliably used to inform policy, as we will discuss later. However, within this analysis we were able, for example, to identify a group of schools (cluster 1) which face significantly greater challenges, based around their 'character' and 'contexts' and on average score far lower on the SPMs.

Another cluster of schools (cluster 4), made up predominantly of Grammar Schools (161 out of the 163 schools in this group had selective admissions policies) scored extremely highly on all 6 SPMs. What is of interest here is that these schools not only had student cohorts with higher average prior attainment (an expected consequence of selection by academic ability), but they also generally had other significant school 'context' and 'character' indicators. They typically had far less students from disadvantaged backgrounds or with special educational needs and were far more likely to have religious character and to be single gender schools. The way that all of these factors interact in their influence of SPMs may be a vital in informing any review of SPMs. Interestingly, when we ran the same hierarchical clustering process for this dataset but with the 'Selective' variable removed, the clusters formed in an almost identical way. The only differences were that 5 schools moved from cluster 4 in the initial analysis to cluster 2 and 6 schools moved from cluster 4 to cluster 2. This demonstrated that it was not simply the binary variable 'Selective' which drove the formation of cluster 4, but the other variables contributed strongly to this process.

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A further schools cluster (cluster 3) demonstrated a much more complex profile. On average their student cohorts had lower than national average prior attainment and higher percentages of disadvantaged students. In general, the percentage of students with special educational needs was below the national average and they were twice as likely to be single gender schools compared to the national patterns. What stands out for this cluster is the average percentage of students with English as an additional language, which is significantly above the national average (66.3% compared to 16.7% nationally). As stated previously, the percentage of English as an additional language students may be problematic in revealing the influence of this aspect of schools on their 'performance' measures, as it fails to incorporate important data, for example the students' first language or their time in English schools (Strand, Malmberg & Hall, 2015). However, here the high numbers of EAL students seems, in general and in combination with other factors, to have a positive influence on some of the SPMs for these schools (in particular Progress 8 and %EBacc Entry) and offsets the effects of the factors which would typically be associated with lower SPMs (i.e., low prior attainment and high levels of disadvantage). Following further exploration, this may be another useful contribution to a review of SPMs.

Further research using these analyses may prove fruitful when seeking to review and reform the design and operationalisation of SPMs to be both fairer and more meaningful. With regard to policy considerations around school funding and the formulae upon it is based, this may also be a platform for work which looks at identifying need and where best to direct resource in order to allow schools to overcome some of these significant and intersecting challenges. Alongside other techniques, cluster analysis may prove to be a useful additional lens through which to view and better understand school 'performance'.

5.5 Limitations and directions for further analysis

For all of the analytical techniques we used a dataset of mainstream state secondary schools in England freely downloaded from the UK Government's "Compare school and college performance in England" website. From that dataset we used 13 variables. This was made up of the 6 headline SPMs and 7 variables classed as 'wider school information' which are routinely used in many other contexts and provide some detail of nature of schools and their intakes. Further work may prove fruitful to conduct the same, or similar, analyses using:

- subsets of the dataset, for example looking at particular groups of schools, or specific geographical areas
- different and wider collections of variables than those used in this project but available in, for example the National Pupil Database and the Schools Workforce Census
- multiple years of equivalent datasets to examine the extent to which the patterns observed here are stable over time.

The clustering evaluation approaches which we used provided no clear, consistent assessment of the quality of the clusters which were formed. However, these techniques may provide a useful basis upon which to refine and evaluate the clustering approaches, using a similar iterative approach to that used in our SEM model development. Alternative clustering approaches, including different clustering algorithms and parameters, could be trialled and then evaluated and the outputs of the different clustering evaluation approaches used to compare the quality of clustering at each stage and to measure the effect of changes made to the algorithm and parameters.

6. Conclusion

The current focus on the effectiveness and consequences of the existing school accountability system prompted us to seek insight into the underlying structure of SPMs. In this study we set out to use innovative statistical approaches, including EFA, CFA, SEM, correlation analysis and cluster analysis, to identify and conceptualise the underlying factors which are represented in the 6 headline SPMs. We wanted to better understand the concept of 'performance' which they capture. This included an assessment of how features which, crucially, are not directly related to the school effectiveness influence the existing SPMs.

This work showed that we can conceptualise the underlying 4 latent constructs which shape 'performance' within SPMs in England. We conceptualised these latent factors as 'attainment', 'progress', 'curriculum' and 'destinations'. We also demonstrated that SPMs in their current form are of limited breadth, with a significant proportion of the metrics devoted just to the measurement and representation of 'attainment'.

While bearing the name of school 'performance' measures, the analysis conducted here suggests that what is actually being measured is strongly influenced by the 'character' of the schools and the 'context' in which they work, rather than simply the quality of the educational provision, as suggested by the term 'performance'. The influence of school 'character' and 'context' is particularly strong for the factor which is represented in half of the headline SPMs, 'attainment'. This analysis contributes to discourse which questions the efficacy of SPMs as proxies of school effectiveness.

Finally, we have seen that cluster analysis, alongside other statistical techniques, may provide further insight into the advantages and challenges which schools face within the current system of school accountability, built as it is around the use of school data and the publication of SPMs. This may, in turn, give clues as to how to address this in an improved design and interpretation of SPMs which is fairer, more accurate and, therefore, more meaningful.

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